
Development of chitosan encapsulated thyme essential oil as an alternative fruit fly repellent for household use

Vivian Wu

Palo Alto High School

Mentor: Cindy Jin

Background

- More people have begun composting to reduce greenhouse gas emissions
- Fruit fly infestations have become a more prevalent issue
- Fruit fly infestation cause unsightly scenes and pose health risks by passing foodborne germs
- Plant essential oils (EOs) have been a source for commercial insect repellents sprays
- However, these insect sprays are of short effect duration and are not suitable for indoor fruit fly infestation control because they are aerosols and can easily contaminate nearby foods

Methodology

PUBMED
Search to
compile list of
insect
repelling EOs

Set up
2-choice fruit
fly repelling
assay & Test
selected EOs

Determine key
parameters
(repelling
efficiency,
loading
efficiency,
encapsulation
efficiency) and
their
measurement
protocol

Prepare
original
prototype
through
homogeniz
ation,
ionization
gelation,
and
vacuum
filtration

Optimization of
the prototype
with different
operating
conditions
(concentration
of EO,
chitosan, and
STPP, select
emulsifier)

Fruit fly repelling assay to determine most effective EO

Experimental
Group

Control

Fruit fly repelling assay to determine most effective EO

$$\text{Repelling Index} = (C-E)/(C+E)$$

C = # of flies in control tube

E = # of flies in experimental group tube

EO with highest repelling index will be selected for product

Fruit fly repelling assay to determine most effective EO

* Generally Recognized As Safe (GRAS) by FDA

Essential oil	Repelling Index		
	Repel-002	Repel-001	Average
Lavender	49.3%	40.0%	44.6%
Rosemary	53.3%	49.2%	51.3%
Bergamot	56.3%	52.9%	54.6%
Camphor	53.1%	61.2%	57.2%
Cinnamon bark	60.6%	62.5%	61.6%
Cedarwood	58.2%	65.6%	61.9%
Tea tree	71.0%	56.9%	63.9%
Spearmint	73.8%	63.6%	68.7%
Oregano	74.6%	69.5%	72.0%
Cinnamon leaf	83.1%	71.4%	77.2%
Eucalyptus	90.6%	87.7%	89.2%
Geranium	91.2%	87.3%	89.2%
Peppermint	90.6%	93.5%	92.1%
Citronella	94.1%	90.6%	92.4%
Lemon eucalyptus	90.5%	96.9%	93.7%
Lemongrass	96.8%	93.3%	95.1%
Clove	96.8%	93.5%	95.2%
Thyme	93.9%	97.0%	95.5%

Results of Preliminary Fruit Fly Assay

Essential Oil	EO quantity (ul)	Average repelling effect	SD
	1	48.4%	7.2%
Citronella	2	96.0%	1.6%
	1	53.3%	11.1%
Peppermint	2	93.9%	2.9%
	1	61.2%	7.3%
Thyme	2	95.9%	1.7%

Optimization of Product Composition

Encapsulation efficiency

	1% Chitosan	2% Chitosan	3% Chitosan
0.5% Thyme oil	26.3%±3.5%	44.2%±3.8%	69.8%±7.6%
1% Thyme oil	29.7%±3.0%	41.6%±4.7%	50.6%±5.1%
2% Thyme oil	24.8%±1.4%	45.8%±3.1%	38.7%±2.3%
3% Thyme oil	21.1%±0.9%	35.2%±3.4%	43.4%±4.1%

Encapsulation efficiency =
total amount of loaded EO /
initial amount of EO × 100

Loading capacity

	1% Chitosan	2% Chitosan	3% Chitosan
0.5% Thyme oil	12.4%±1.6%	10.4%±0.9%	10.9%±1.2%
1% Thyme oil	27.9%±2.8%	19.6%±2.2%	15.9%±1.6%
2% Thyme oil	46.6%±2.7%	43.1%±3.0%	24.3%±1.4%
3% Thyme oil	59.5%±2.7%	49.7%±4.8%	40.8%±3.8%

Loading capacity = total
amount of loaded EO /
weight of product × 100

Thyme Oil Calibration Curve

Composition and Yield of Prototype

Composition			Yield	
Chitosan concentration	Thyme oil concentration	Tween 80 concentration	Encapsulation efficiency	Loading capacity
2%	2%	1%	65.1±3.5%	61.2±3.3%

Thyme oil-encapsulated chitosan sheet placed in an organza bag and a petri dish.

Preserved Thyme Oil Content Over Time

	Fresh	Week 1	Week 2	Week 4	Week 6
Thyme oil content ($\mu\text{l} / 10 \text{ mg}$)	2.90 ± 0.08	2.85 ± 0.27	2.99 ± 0.27	2.89 ± 0.16	2.98 ± 0.15
Repelling effect	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Future Work / Conclusion

- Encapsulating thyme oil in chitosan achieved 100% effective and environmentally friendly pest repelling product
- Further studies will be conducted to determine the long-term stability of the prototype
- Although the current product showed 100% fruit fly repelling efficiency, eggs and larvae already existing in the compost bin may still develop into adult flies
- Assays for more encapsulating materials (e.g., other natural polymers such as agar, gelatin, and alginate) to determine optimal encapsulation

